

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Regarding Mechanical Ventilation Among Nurses Working in Selected Hospital in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined knowledge, attitude and practice regarding mechanical ventilation among nurses working in selected hospital in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. The researcher adopted a descriptive design for the study. Four research questions and three corresponding hypotheses. Literature was reviewed under: conceptual framework, theoretical framework, empirical review and summary of literature review. The population of the study comprised one hundred eighty eight (188) nurses from selected hospitals in Owerri Capital territory, Imo State. Due to the manageable size of the population, no sample and sampling technique was used. The instrument used for data collection is a researcher made questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha reliability test method which yielded positive correlation with value of .89 which indicates high reliability. The research questions were answered using percentages while the hypotheses were tested using Bi-variable and multivariable analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The major findings are that 127(71%) of nurses have sufficient knowledge toward mechanical ventilation. Also, findings showed that 53(29%) of nurses have insufficient knowledge toward mechanical ventilation. The finding of this study also revealed that the highest possible score (positive attitude) was 154(86%) whilst the lowest possible score (negative attitude) was 36(20%). The findings in this study also suggest that 120 (75.86%) of the respondents practice mechanical ventilation while 60 (24.14%) do not practice. The findings in this study also suggest that 144 (75.8%) of the responders reported there is no guideline of mechanical ventilation in the unit they are currently working. 160 (84.2%) of professionals reported they have never received any continuing professional education (Update) special training on mechanical ventilation. The result of the hypotheses revealed that there is no significant relationship between socio-demographic variables sex, age and current working area with knowledge, attitude and practice toward mechanical ventilation. Knowledge, attitude and practice had statistically significant association with mechanical ventilation. The researcher recommends among others that the Federal Ministry of Health must consider expanding Critical care medicine with optimal mechanical ventilation delivery systems in the country to address critically ill patients.

Keywords: knowledge, attitude, practice r, mechanical, ventilation, nurses selected hospital Owerri.

Introduction

One life-saving support measure that can make the difference between a severely ill patient's recovery and death is mechanical ventilation. Primary or secondary respiratory lung pathology is the most frequent cause of admission for adult patients to the intensive care unit (ICU) [1]. However, failing to recognize unfavorable effects and using the ventilator inappropriately in relation to lung disease can have serious consequences for the patient and lead to a number of complications, some of which may be life-threatening [2]. Mechanical ventilation provides distinct problems to the nurse, as each patient is unique in terms of lung pathology and the type of ventilation strategy and settings required for the specific lung pathology of the individual patient [3]

Inappropriate ventilator settings, failure by the nurse to notice declining lung function and problems can lead to ventilator induced lung damage (VILI), which may exacerbate the original disease of the lungs [4]. As such this can lead to problems such as pneumothorax, tracheal necrosis, and ventilator related pneumonia [5]. In the worst case scenario, these issues may result in higher patient morbidity and death as well as an extended hospital stay, which would raise expenses dramatically [6]. In contemporary nursing and medical systems, the care of critically sick patients has grown in significance. In order to maximize patient outcomes, reduce injury, and increase the efficacy of mechanical breathing, critical care nurses are essential [7]. The skills and knowledge of health teams regarding the care of a patient on a mechanical ventilator and patients' clinical status enable them to intune ventilator settings to maximize the benefits of ventilator support while minimizing complications [8]

Inadequate nurses' understanding of ventilator modes, their limitations, causes of distress, ventilator desynchronization, and proper management allows them to deliver high-quality care at a higher altitude [9]. Given that nurses are the first-line managers who deal with issues involving patients and ventilators, it is essential to identify issues like respiratory distress, dyspnea, and increased respiratory effort and to know how to address them [10]. The basic ventilator support, such as ventilator mode, setting, and alarms, must therefore be understood by the nurses who care for patients on ventilators. It is also necessary to be adept in immediately identifying and resolving common patient and ventilator-related difficulties to offer optimal patient-centered care and avert consequences [11]

Studies have shown that ICU nurses' knowledge, altitude and practice on mechanical ventilation is globally poor. A study conducted in South Africa has reported that even in high-income countries where nursing education is advanced, the levels of knowledge on mechanical ventilation are not perfect [12]. This study is therefore expected to be important since it aims to gather additional information about the knowledge, altitude, and practice of ICU nurses regarding the use of mechanical ventilators. The critically ill patients in the intensive care units are typically in need of mechanical life support. The care of these patients on mechanical ventilation depends on medical personnel, especially nurses [13]. The health or death of patients in intensive care units can be determined by the nursing staff's expertise and proficiency [14]. The sophisticated equipment in today's intensive care units necessitates quick nursing attention [15].

The advanced technology in the critical care units cannot benefit unless integrated with the patients' condition; neither can these technologies help patients unless nurses demonstrate critical knowledge and understanding regarding these mechanical devices [16]. However, it is frequently found in the critical care literature that nurses working in the intensive care units usually lack basic knowledge and competence about the ventilator mechanics in relation to the respiratory physiology, which questions the quality of care and safety of intubated patients [17]

Positive pressure invasive ventilation, a mechanical intervention, is the most frequent reason for intensive care unit admissions, according to [18]. For nursing to be proactive in a critical care context, expertise knowledge and altitude are necessary. Since nurses are the primary source of information for patients, family members, and other members of the interdisciplinary team, it is imperative that they possess the pertinent knowledge and abilities needed for their position [10]. Additionally, they said that nurses can enhance patient outcomes, shorten hospital stays, and lower the risk of complications if they had the necessary knowledge and abilities. Patients on mechanical ventilator are totally depended on nurses. So, the nursing personnel have a major role to play in sustaining the lives of the patients by meeting health requirements. Thus, for this, a thorough knowledge and skills regarding the nursing care of patients on mechanical ventilator is very much essential [20].

Nurses play a vital role in contributing to patients' health and recovery in the high dependency areas since many ventilator – related decisions are made based on nurses' collaboration with doctors. Inappropriate ventilator settings in association with the respiratory pathologies and inability of nurses to identify potential deterioration can result in severe consequences, various complications, and prolong hospital stay. A data from a clinical survey (n=38 nurses) revealed that 62% of the mechanically ventilated patients suffered through breathlessness due to nurses' failure of recognizing the ventilator parameters [21]. Similarly, a quantitative descriptive study revealed that intensive care nursing staff showed poor knowledge and competence related to the ventilator mechanics and mechanical ventilation [22]. Moreover, the results of an audit of Critical Care Society of Southern Africa highlighted that 75 % of the intensive care nurses lacked basic understanding and competence related to the fundamental ventilator mechanics; but were still independently dealing with the intubated patients. Likewise, a study conducted in Sudan, utilizing the pre-test and post-test method, illustrated that nurses had poor scores for knowledge and altitude to practice about ventilator mechanics and its associated complications in the pre-test, but the scores significantly improved in the post-test ($P < 0.05$) after the introduction of an educational training session [23]. According to a study, the mean mortality rate in the intensive care units is 50% in Pakistan. Similarly, a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted in Sialkot, also identified a mortality rate of 51.7% among intubated patients in Pakistan with 32% related to the ventilator associated events, which include incompetence in ventilator handling and adequate knowledge about its functioning resulting in various nosocomial

infections such ventilator associated pneumonia and patients' distress [24]. Being the central care providers, nurses can play a pivotal role in decreasing the incidences of such events. Successful mechanical ventilation needs a fundamental and comprehensive understanding of human respiratory functioning and ventilator dynamics along with the intensive nursing care [25]

Initial lung issues may be caused by a variety of pulmonary diseases and injuries as a result of inappropriate ventilator settings and nurses' failure to recognize related declines in pulmonary functioning. Numerous illnesses linked to ventilators are also caused by inadequate handling and a lack of information about them. With a prevalence rate of at least 70%, ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) is the most common infection in Pakistan's intensive care units. A cross-sectional study with 100 nurses in Pakistan's public and commercial hospitals' intensive care units revealed that nurses' ignorance about and inability to use mechanical ventilation contributed to a rise in cases.

A prospective audit of 126 mechanically ventilated patients conducted in the intensive care unit of a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan revealed aspiration of secretions into lungs and blockage of endotracheal tube as the most frequent complications of mechanical ventilation that indicate lack of staff knowledge and competencies while dealing with ventilators. Nurses dealing with intubated patients should have basic understanding of the ventilator mechanics in association to the respiratory physiology to identify potentially adverse events, prevent complications, and facilitate weaning [26]. However, limited studies were found internationally that assessed nurses' knowledge about the ventilator mechanics and respiratory physiology, and no such study was found in the Pakistani context. It provided the researchers an opportunity to assess the baseline knowledge of nursing staff about basic ventilator mechanics and respiratory physiology, educate them to improve patient care, and re-assess their knowledge. Hence, the study aimed to assess the baseline assessment of knowledge, altitude and practice regarding mechanical ventilation among nurses working in Selected Hospital in Owerri, Imo State.

The patients in the intensive care units are acutely sick, usually dependent on life supporting mechanical devices. The life of these mechanically ventilated patients is reliant on healthcare professionals, particularly nurses, for care. Caring for the patient on mechanical ventilation has become an integral part of nursing care especially in critical care unit, intensive Care units (ICU), critical care units (CCU), emergency departments and progressive care units (PCU).

Positive patient outcomes depend on an understanding of nurses to the principles of mechanical ventilation and goals of the therapy, weaning plans, and patient tolerance of changes in ventilator setting [22].

Current research about nurses' knowledge, altitude and practice of mechanical ventilation mainly shows that majority of nurses does not have the knowledge and right altitude of operation of mechanical ventilation, while studies of comprehensive nursing interventions for mechanical ventilation systems are lacking. This may be due to the fact that nursing staff may not be responsible for mechanical ventilation systems in Nigeria. Furthermore, the mechanical ventilation proffers various challenges to nurses due to the unique nature of several lung pathologies requiring different types of artificial ventilation. And the fact that inappropriate ventilator settings in association with the respiratory pathologies and inability of nurses to identify potential deterioration can result in severe consequences, various complications, and prolong hospital stay. A data from a clinical survey revealed that 62% of the mechanically ventilated patients suffered through breathlessness due to nurses' failure of recognizing the ventilator parameters [27]

Similarly, a quantitative descriptive study revealed that intensive care nursing staff showed poor knowledge and competence related to the ventilator mechanics and mechanical ventilation. Moreover, the results of an audit of Critical Care Society of Southern Africa highlighted that 75 % of the intensive care nurses lacked basic understanding and competence related to the fundamental ventilator mechanics; but were still independently dealing with the intubated patients. Likewise, a study conducted in Sudan, utilizing the pre-test and post-test method, illustrated that nurses had poor scores for knowledge about ventilator mechanics and associated complications in the pre-test, but the scores significantly improved in the post-test ($P < 0.05$) after the introduction of an educational training session. Similarly, a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted in Sialkot, also identified a mortality rate of 51.7% among intubated patients in Pakistan with 32% related to the ventilator associated events, which include incompetence in ventilator handling and inadequate knowledge about its functioning resulting in various nosocomial infections such ventilator associated pneumonia and patients' distress. Being the central care providers, nurses can play a pivotal role in decreasing the incidences of such events. Successful mechanical ventilation needs a fundamental and comprehensive understanding of human respiratory functioning and ventilator dynamics along with the intensive nursing care. Therefore, no study has ever been done to investigate the assessment of knowledge, attitude and practice regarding mechanical ventilation among nurses working in selected hospital in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria thus the necessity to embark on the study.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

The research design adopted in this study was a descriptive survey.

Area of Study

The study was conducted at five hospitals in Owerri Capital territory of Imo State. Owerri Capital territory is the regional capital of Imo State.

Ethical Consideration

An ethical approval from Imo State University Teaching Hospital was obtained

The consent of each volunteered nurse from each hospital visited was sought before they were used for the study thereby not infringing on their rights (as their participation was voluntary).

Population of the Study

The population for the study comprised Nurses working in emergency departments, intensive care units including NICU, PICU, and Post anesthetics care units from selected hospitals in Owerri Capital territory of Imo State. The population is estimated to be one hundred eighty eight (188) nurses from selected hospitals in Owerri Capital territory, Imo State.

Table 1: Populations of hospitals who offer services based on critical care and have mechanical ventilators within Owerri Capital territory of Imo State,2024

	Selected hospitals	Population
1	Federal university teaching hospital	88
2	Save a life international hospital	21
3	Mark of glory Specialist hospital	22
4	Dews of hope Specialist hospital	21
5	Umuguma Specialist hospital	36
	Total	188

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

Nurses currently working and having a year or more experience in the emergency departments and intensive care units, including NICU, PICU, and Post anesthetics care units, are willing to participate in the study.

Nurses who are willing to participate

Exclusion Criteria

Nurses who are on sick leave, maternity leave and annual leave.

Instruments for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was the researcher made instrument titled “assessment of knowledge, attitude and practice regarding mechanical ventilation among nurses working in selected hospital in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. It was designed and framed by the researcher from review of literature to elicit information for the respondents (nurses). The questionnaire comprises five sections, Section A B, C, D and E. Section A demographic information of respondents, section B comprised of ten (10) items on knowledge regarding mechanical ventilation, section C attitude of nurses on the mechanical ventilation, section D practice of nurses on the mechanical ventilation and section E factors associated with KAP on nurses regarding mechanical ventilation. The respondents were expected to respond to the options provided. The response pattern was the modified four-point Likert Scale. The responses were given values as shown below: Strongly agreed (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A)= 3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 points and strongly disagree (SD)=1 points

Validity of the Instrument

The research instrument was developed and was given to the project supervisor for constructive critics and to assess whether it was capable of collecting the required data, thereafter corrections were made. The questionnaire was returned to the project supervisor for approval.

Reliability of the Instrument

The instrument was checked for reliability over time, and that the contents have internal consistency. The test-retest reliability was used to measure the correlational coefficient between the variables, where a pre-test was also used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. Ten copies of the questionnaire were distributed to nurses in Federal Medical Center, Umuahia different from the study population (respondents) and same were collected after. Ten days later, the same but fresh copies of the questionnaire were distributed again to the same nurses in the intensive care unit. The results were collected, tallied and analyzed using Cronbach Alpha reliability test method which yielded positive correlation with value of .89 which indicates high reliability.

Method of Data Collection

Prior to data collection, initial visits was made to each Selected Hospital the researcher with an introductory letter from Head of Department of selected Hospital and the ethical approval letter to introduce self and the purpose of the visit. These visits provided a forum for introduction and establishment of rapport between the researchers and the nurses in the departments.

With the help of one (1) research assistants, one hundred and eighty eight (188) questionnaires will be administered to the workers on the spot in their departments, after obtaining informed (written) consent, within the time permitted by the director. The questionnaires were shared took one week. This enabled the workers to completely fill the questionnaires and were collected from the workers immediately after completion. Confidentiality and anonymity was maintained.

Statistical Analysis

The data was coded, entered and cleaned using EPI Data version 3.1 and then exported into SPSS statistical software version 26 for analysis. Descriptive statistical analysis such as simple frequencies, measures of central tendency, and variability measures will be used to describe the characteristics of participants. Then the information was presented using frequencies, summary measures, tables and figures. Bi-variable and multivariable analysis will be used to see the association between each independent variable and the outcome variable, using binary logistic regression Analysis. Chi-square test was done and variables that show P -value of ≤ 0.05 with 95% CI was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

In this chapter, the results of data collected are arranged and presented.

Table 1: Demographic data of respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency=180	Percentage %
Age	21-29	54	30
	30- 39	100	55.6
	40-49	20	2.8
	>49	6	0.6
Gender	Male	25	37.7
	Female	155	86.1
Departments nurses are currently working	NICU	25	9.4
	PICU	30	8.9
	ICU	65	47.8
	ED	60	33.3
Educational Status	MSc Nurse	6	3.3
	RN/RM	143	79.4
	Diploma Nurse	5	2.8
	Others	6	3.3

Data on table 1 show the demographic characteristics of the respondents. A total of 188 nurses working in five selected public hospitals in Owerri, Imo State were included for this study, only 180 of them responded for the questionnaire, making the response rate of 95.7%.

The minimum and maximum age of respondents was 21 and 50 years respectively. Regarding sex of respondents, 25 (55.6%) were males. More than half, 114 (63.3%) of the respondents were females in the age group 30-39. Most participants 143 (79.4%) had RN/RM 86 (47.8%) of the nurses are working in adult ICU.

Table 2: Frequency distribution of knowledge regarding mechanical ventilation among nurses working in selected hospital in Owerri, Imo State (N=180)

No.	Knowledge Variables		Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Mechanical ventilation is like any other machine.	1.True	75	41.7
		2. False	105	58.3
2	Mechanical ventilation is not medication but a supportive therapy	1.True	146	81.1
		2. False	34	18.9
3	Mechanical ventilation should only be given doctors' supervision.	1.True	82	45.6
		2. False	98	54.4
4	Mechanical ventilation promotes oxygen circulation	1.True	132	73.3
		2. False	48	26.7
5	Can be administered in severe respiratory distress	1.True	169	93.9
		2. False	11	6.1
6	Can be administered in severe clinical anemia.	1.True	113	62.8
		2. False	67	37.2
7	Can be administered for eclampsia	1.True	134	74.4
		2. False	46	25.
8	Can be administered for restlessness and convulsion in children	1.True	168	93.3
		2. False	12	6.7
Overall Knowledge		Good knowledge	127(71)	
		Poor Knowledge	53(29)	

Data on table 2 show that respondents were asked 8 knowledge based questions to assess nurses' knowledge regarding mechanical ventilation and they are categorized into two groups based on their score (Good knowledge and Poor Knowledge). Total cumulative knowledge level was determined to be 127(71%) and 53(29%). Hence the result is considered "Sufficient knowledge" while the rest was considered "Insufficient knowledge". Findings of this study revealed that the majority of nurses who participated in this study had sufficient knowledge score, 127(71%).

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of nurses attitude towards mechanical ventilation among nurses working in selected hospital in Owerri, Imo State

No.	Description	Positive%	Negative%
1	Mechanical ventilation should only be administered by a doctor order	140(76.3)	40(23.7)
2	Oral and nasal hygiene and bed bathing should be done when patient is on mechanical ventilation	166(92.2)	14(7.7)
3	Continuous mechanical ventilation administration is more beneficial than intermittent mechanical ventilation	100(55.5)	80(45.3)
4	Humidification is the best practice to prevent dryness of mucus membrane of upper respiratory tract causing soreness	170(94.4)	10(5.5)
5	Persons with severe lung disease need to be maintained at the prescribed mechanical ventilation saturation range	158(88.7)	22(12.2)

6	Since mechanical ventilation is a not drug its administration must be monitored effectively for a good prognosis to be recorded.	137(76.1)	43(23.8)
7	A patient on mechanical ventilation indicates that the patient is at the end stage of life and needs empathy.	171(95.0)	9(5)
Overall attitude of nurses		Positive	Negative
		154(85.5)	26(14.4)

Data on table 3 show the response on the level of attitude of nurses toward mechanical ventilation was dichotomized as positive and negative. The highest possible score (positive attitude) was 149(82.7%) whilst the lowest possible score (negative attitude) was 31 (17.2%). This means that majority of the nurses, 154(86) have positive attitude towards mechanical ventilation of critically ill patient.

Table 4: Frequency distribution of practice of mechanical ventilation among nurses working in selected hospital in Owerri, Imo State

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage%	
Type II respiratory failure Practice	Nasal catheter at 1-2 L/min/ in the absence of Venturi masks	106	58.9
	Nasal catheter at 16 L/min	35	19.4
	Ventilation mask with reservoir	39	21.7
	6- 9L/min		
Type I respiratory failure practice	FiO2 of 60%	108	60
	FiO2 of 20%	40	22.2
	FiO2 of 150%	32	17.8
Humidification is essential for patients receiving oxygen through one of the following device	Endotracheal tube or a tracheostomy	18	10
	Nasal Prong	149	82.8
	Ventilation mask	13	7.2
Regarding weaning and discontinuation of mechanical ventilation which of the following statement is true?	started if clinically stable on low dose oxygen	131	72.8
	commenced after a new chest radiograph is normal	36	20
	clinically stable on high-dose oxygen	13	7.2
Which of the following condition can not affect Pulse Mechanical ventilation monitoring/reading	Patient motion or fitting	9	5
	Carbon-monoxide poisoning	16	8.9
	Jaundice and anemia	15	8.3
	False nails, nail varnish	140	77.8
Which of the following is the best in pulse Mechanical ventilation practice	The wave form and/or signal strength must be optimal	139	77.2
	A blood pressure cuff on the arm	26	14.4

	of probe will lead to a false SPO2 reading		
	A blood pressure cuff on the arm	15	8.3
	of probe will lead to a correct reading		
Which of the following method help to reduce the risk of side effects associated with dry gas administration and to promote patient comfort?	Use face mask	10	5.6
	Use nasal cannula	3	1.7
	Attach humidification device	127	70.6
	Attach Pulseoxymeter	26	14.4
	All	14	7.8
What will be the effect of collection of water in the tubing during mechanical ventilation administration?	Can partially or completely occlude the flow of oxygen	21	11.7
	Empty the collected water in the tubing as needed	29	16.1
	Facilitates flow of oxygen and promote patient comfort	130	72.2
Which of the following mechanical ventilation delivery device can provide 60 – 90% of oxygen used for short term treatment during trauma?	Nasal catheter	26	14.4
	Venturi masks and adapters	13	7.2
	Non- rebreathing ventilation mask	71	39.4
	Tracheostomy mask	3	1.7
	All	67	37.2
Which nursing intervention is not appropriate during Mechanical ventilation?	Mouth care	6	3.3
	Encourage adequate fluid intake	19	10.6
	Apply water based cream if lips or nose become dry	15	8.3
	Apply petroleum jelly to minimize inflammation of lips and nose	140	77.8

Data on table 4 show the responses of the nurses on practice of mechanical ventilation among nurses. The lowest possible score (poor practice) was 1 whilst the highest possible score (Good practice) was 9. The level of practice of nurses toward mechanical ventilation was dichotomized as Good with practice score of less than mean and poor with practice score of greater than or equal to mean. From all of the participants 79 (43.9%) had unsatisfactory practice towards mechanical ventilation, while 101 (56.1%) had satisfactory practice towards mechanical ventilation.

Table 5: Frequency distribution of factors associated with KAP on nurses regarding mechanical ventilation among nurses working in selected hospital in Owerri, Imo State

Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Is there guideline of mechanical ventilation in the unit you are currently working	Yes	44	24.4
	No	136	75.6
Have you received any CPE/ update/ special training on mechanical ventilation?	Yes	29	16.1
	No	151	83.9
Is there adequate supply of mechanical ventilation devices in your working unit?	Yes	67	37.2
	No	113	62.8
Are your patients administered mechanical ventilation paid/ charged for the service?	Yes	13	7.2
	No	165	91.7
Do you get the amount of oxygen cylinders equivalent to the label written?	Yes	87	48.3
	No	44	24.4
Is there periodic maintenance of mechanical ventilation equipment or devices?	Yes	100	55.6
	No	80	44.4
What is your source of Medical/Nursing training information concerning mechanical ventilation	In service training.	157	87.2
	Critical care training	46	25.
	Colleagues	8	4.4
	Print and electronic media	1	0.6
	Others	7	3.9
Do you know that using wrong parameters in mechanical ventilation in emergency room may contribute to carbon dioxide retention?	Yes	156	8.9
	No	16	4.4
Do you think work load/ burden in the work place affects your practice on Mechanical ventilation monitoring	Yes	166	92.2
	No	14	7.9
In what format does the physician prescribe mechanical ventilation	Written	128	28.9
	Oral	52	71.1
Do you often face unclear or incomplete written prescription for mechanical ventilation?	Yes	20	86.1
	No	155	11.1
How long ago did you administer mechanical ventilation to a patient?	≤6months	155	86.1
	6-12 months	5	2.8
	>12 months	20	11.1
Indication for Acute mechanical ventilation include Respiratory distress (respiratory rate >40/min in adult or 60 in neonate)	Yes	149	82.8
	No	31	18.2

Data on table 4 show the responses of the nurses on factors associated with KAP on nurses regarding mechanical ventilation. 144 (75.8%) of the responders reported there is no guideline of mechanical ventilation in the unit they are currently working. 160 (84.2%) of professionals reported they have never received any continuing professional education (Update) special training on mechanical ventilation. 118 (62.1%) of nurses reported there is inadequate supply of mechanical ventilation in their working units, while a close minority of patients reported there is inadequacy. 174 (91.6%) of nurses reported that, patients administered mechanical ventilation without extra payment. 91(47.9%) of responders responded they get mechanical ventilation cylinders equivalent to the label written. 105 (55.3%) of nurses reported there is periodic maintenance of mechanical ventilation equipment.

Regarding individual factors, 166 (87.4%) of nurses reported the source of information concerning mechanical ventilation remained medical/nursing training. In addition, 164 (86.3%) of responders acknowledged that using short time mechanical ventilation in emergency room may contribute to carbon dioxide retention. 175 (92.1%) of nurses reported workload/ burden in the work place affects mechanical ventilation delivery. Significant majority of nurses i.e. 131 (68.9%) reported to have received oral mechanical ventilation prescription from physician. 162 (85.3%) of nurses reported to have faced unclear or incomplete written prescription. 164 (86.3%) reported to have administered mechanical ventilation with in the past 6 months.

Discussion

According to the study, 100 (55.6%) were males. More than half, 114 (63.3%) of the respondents were females in the age group 30-39. minimum and maximum age of respondents was 21 and 50 years Most participants 163 (90.6%) had first degree. 86 (47.8%) of the nurses are working in adult ICU.

Findings revealed that 127(71%) of nurses have sufficient knowledge toward mechanical ventilation. Also findings showed that 53(29%) of nurses have insufficient knowledge toward mechanical ventilation respectively. This discrepancy might be due to lack of trainings on area of mechanical ventilation, socio-demographic differences, differences in work experience, study time gap and study setting difference. Findings from [28] contrast this result in the report of their study conducted in Turkey, Egypt, Eriteria and Addis Ababa reported overall knowledge to be 27.5%, 18%, 43.3% and 36.2% respectively. This implies the responsibility of hospital management for providing the staff skills development program while updating the knowledge of the staff nurses is a paramount factor in professional performing. There is a need to update the knowledge of staff nurses, training is essential and should be integrated into their work schedule regularly.

The finding of this study also revealed that the highest possible score (positive attitude) was 154(86%) whilst the lowest possible score (negative attitude) was 36(20%). This means that majority of the nurses have positive attitude towards mechanical ventilation of critically ill patient. This finding is supported by that of [29] is comparable with those conducted in Saudi Arabia and three public hospitals in Addis Ababa hospital that reported cumulative attitude to be positive in 32.8% and 53.3% of nurses respectively (17,28). This difference in nurses' attitude toward mechanical ventilation of patients might be due to geographical, cultural and social variable which govern the research environments or be due to difference in question measuring nurses attitude toward mechanical ventilation of patient.

The findings in this study also suggest that 120 (75.86%) of the respondents practice mechanical ventilation while 60 (24.14%) do not practice. According to [30] who stated that studies from Egypt, Rwanda and Eretria reported satisfactory practice among nurses to be 18%, 46.2%, 45% and 43.4% respectively, all of these findings are lower than this study finding. These differences can be due to different measurement tool, lack of training of nurses on mechanical ventilation, difference in socioeconomic background, lack of formal mechanical ventilation education and absence of independent critical care medicine units equipped to deal with sustainable mechanical ventilation in the former studies. Meanwhile a study from Iranian hospital reported good practice among nurses to be 74.5% which is significantly higher than this report. These could be as a result of sustainable mechanical ventilation, better nursing care, continuous in service nurse training, well equipped critical care centers and better staff communication in the Iranian setup.

The findings in this study also suggest that 144 (75.8%) of the responders reported there is no guideline of mechanical ventilation in the unit they are currently working. 160 (84.2%) of professionals reported they have never received any continuing professional education (Update) special training on mechanical ventilation. The study also revealed factors such as unfavourable professional attitude, low job motivation, limited professional accountability, inadequate or inappropriate equipment, heavy workload, staff shortage, inadequate staff training and ineffective supervision were reported as barriers to oral care in ICUs. This is in line with [31], other contributing barriers include, lack of education, lack of policies and protocols, lack of resources and the shortage of staff, lack of mechanical ventilation, equipment, absence of guidelines, time constraints, poor supervision, and high workload.

Conclusion

Majority of nurses had knowledge and satisfactory practice toward mechanical ventilation. It was found that Knowledge and practice had statistically significant association with routine practice of mechanical ventilation, presence of guidelines in the working units and presence of written prescriptions from physicians. Nurses attitude was found to have statistically significant relation with their practice towards mechanical ventilation.

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